

THE DETERMINING ROLE OF THE COMMUNICATIVE INTENTION IN ACHIEVING POSITIVE EFFECT IN HUMOR TEXTS

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Abstract: *This article deals with the determining role of the communicative intention in achieving positive effect in humor. Moreover, different approaches of scientist to humor and the results of their researches highlighted by the author.*

Key Words: *Individual humor, cyclical, "punch line", creative thinking, interlocutors, cognitive experience, physiological level, "mirthful".*

Humor, both producing and appreciating, underpins positive social interactions. It acts as a facilitator of communication. There are clear links to wellbeing that go along with this form of social engagement. We all know that humor plays many roles in our lives. Not only is it useful to entertain and to amuse, but it can also serve to break the ice and put people at ease. It can ameliorate awkward situations and assuage tense ones. For this reason, it's viable as a consideration in communicating with diplomacy and tact. There is not a large body of research on humor, but much of it centers on humor in organizations, like the workplace. Humor events are defined as "discrete social behaviors that a producer intentionally creates for an audience that influences audience positive affect." Such audience positive affect can be transmitted to others through emotional contagion, or the idea that emotional states are contagious; to illustrate, consider how you feel when you are around someone who is depressed, versus someone who is happy and uplifting. Further, such shared positive affect will

contribute to constructing an environment conducive to additional humor events.

In this way, humor is circular; therefore, humor events in isolation do not need to have much effect on individual or group general sentiment in order to influence individual and group outcomes. Instead, humor events are part of a cyclical and cumulative process. Individual humor events within this process each have an incremental influence on individual and group feeling (affect), and also lay a foundation for additional humor events. Researchers offer various definitions and functions of humor. Some suggest that it "consists of amusing communications that produce positive emotions and cognitions in the individual, group, or organization." Others assert that humor is "any event shared by an agent (e.g. an employee) with another individual (i.e. a target) that is intended to be amusing to the target and that the target perceives as an intentional act." Further, researchers have identified several functions of humor, including coping, stress-relief, defense mechanism, bonding and cohesiveness, ingratiation, power, control, aggression, and the subversion of power.

Some scholars have devoted some time to considering how humor works, and have developed theories explaining it. Perhaps the most supported and useful is known as incongruity theory, which asserts that humor "results from the experience of incongruity and its appreciation or resolution." For example, stand-alone jokes work because they simultaneously evoke two seemingly unrelated systems of expectation. The "punch line" bridges these systems to resolve the incongruity. We experience pleasure in making an unexpected connection within this resolution. Such a connection has been likened to the feeling associated with solving a puzzle, and to cognitive "play." Incongruity and its appreciation exist in comments, quips, puns, and other behaviors, not only stand-alone jokes. Sarcastic comments contain incongruity between what is spoken and what is intended. Violations of social norms are incongruous in expected, versus actual, behaviors.

Most definitions of humor are essentialist in that they try to list the necessary and sufficient conditions something must meet in order to be counted as humor. Some theories isolate a common element supposedly found in all humor, but hold back from making claims about the sufficient conditions. Many theorists seem to confuse offering the necessary conditions for a response to count as humor with explaining why we find one thing funny rather than another. This second question, what would be sufficient for an object to be found funny, is the Holy Grail of humor studies,

and must be kept distinct from the goals of a definition of the humor response. The Holy Grail is often confused with a question regarding the sufficient conditions for our response to count as humorous amusement, but a crucial distinction needs to be made: identifying the conditions of a response is different from the isolating the features something must possess in order to provoke such a response. The first task is much different from suggesting what features are sufficient to provoke a response of humorous amusement. What amounts to a humor response is different from what makes something humorous. The noun (humor) and adjectival (humorous) senses of the term are difficult to keep distinct due to the imprecision of our language in this area. Much of the dissatisfaction with traditional humor theories can be traced back to an equivocation between these two senses of the term.

Humor is found to be an essential element of creative thinking in Western culture. In Eastern culture, however, the relationship between creativity and humor is ambivalent. This study examined the relationship among humor styles, creative personality traits, and creative thinking abilities. A sample of 118 Chinese undergraduates in Hong Kong was recruited to complete the Humor Styles Questionnaire, the three Creative Personality subscales of the Chinese Personality Assessment Inventory-2 (CPAI-2), and the Verbal Test of the Wallach-Kogan Creativity Tests. Results show that humor styles are uncorrelated with creative thinking abilities of flexibility, fluency, and originality, but affiliative humor and aggressive humor are correlated with creative personality traits of novelty and diversity. A hierarchical multiple regression shows that both humor styles and creative personality traits of novelty and diversity account for non-significant variance on creative thinking abilities. These findings largely support a hypothesized non-association between humor styles and creative measures. They also pose a sharp contrast to findings obtained in the West, in which humor styles are typically correlated with both creative thinking abilities and creative personality traits. Evidence suggests that in dyadic conversations some alignment occurs at the physiological level, but relatively little is known about the conditions that may facilitate physiological synchrony of two interlocutors. In the present interdisciplinary study, the impact of specific linguistic features of ongoing dialogues-the use of humor-related communication elements-was examined in 24 male dyads who were meeting for the first time. Heart rate synchrony was quantified using phase synchronization, which reflects the degree of moment-to-moment adjustments that occur between the two persons of a

dyad. Comical hypotheticals and verbal amplifiers were identified and quantified using cognitive-linguistic methods of corpus analysis.

Additionally, smiles following these communication elements were identified using the Facial Action Coding System. The data showed that the heart rate time series of the two interlocutors were to some extent synchronized in phase, and that the magnitude of this synchronization exceeded what had to be expected by chance. The strength of heart rate synchrony in a dyad was the higher the more comical hypotheticals were produced, independently from how much the two conversation partners were in sum talking to each other. A similar observation was made for verbal amplifiers, but their effect depended on whether they were perceived (and acknowledged by a smile) as humorous. The findings are in line with the more general notion that physiological synchrony may be enhanced by shared experience and suggest that the use of (reciprocated) humor may speed up the building of rapport among communication partners.

To sum up all facts above, it should be noted that several major theories claim to comprehensively explain how humor originates in the minds of those experiencing it. Humor is viewed as a cognitive experience involving an internal redefining of sociocultural reality and resulting in a “mirthful” state of mind, of which laughter is a possible external display. Laughter is a primary indicator of the experience of humor, but it is not the only one. Smiles, grins, or even sudden exhalations can indicate such experience. The perceptionor audience-centered nature of humor is highlighted by the fact that, other than through such nonlinguistic indicators, the only evidence of humor experience comes from statements by the person experiencing it.

REFERENCES:

1. Michael Kern. (2017). Humor Advantage.
2. Paulson, Terry L. (2013). Making Humor Work. Menlo Park, California, Crisp Leaning.com.
3. Stanley Danwood. (2014). Humor.
4. <https://stanfield.com/the-importance-of-humor-in-the-classroom/>